

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D2.3

Dissemination and Communication Plan

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Executive Summary

This document introduces the RELIANCE project dissemination and communication plan and strategy detailing its core messages and targets. It defines the progressive Dissemination and Communication implementation plan of the consortium to ensure visibility, sharing of information with other EOSC-related projects, services providers and scientific communities. The objective is to ensure the widest promotion of RELIANCE services and the overall project during the grant period. This document also acts as a reference framework in order to constantly monitor and evaluate the communication and dissemination activities impact. It will be updated accordingly to project activities and potential new synergies with other project or initiatives. The list of events and collaborations will be constantly updated and adjusted as the project progresses. The updates and initial results of the communication and dissemination plan will be included in Deliverable D2.4 at M12.

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
DCP	Dissemination and Communication plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
RO	Research Objects

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1 Introduction

The present RELIANCE Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) is drafted at M3 in the context of RELIANCE WP2 “Outreach exploitation and capacity building” framework. It is a reference document to be used by the RELIANCE consortium partners to carefully plan and implement their contribution to the dissemination and communication actions foreseen by the project.

The document provides an overview of project stakeholders’ categories, key messages and key performance indicators, matching them with the tools and channels to be used to reach each target during the project.

The document also is a working document to the project management and WP responsible as a living reference to evaluate the impact of dissemination and communication activities. It will be therefore updated during the duration of the project whenever needed.

The document is organized as follows:

- **Chapter 1** is providing the overall context which is needed by all project partners to understand and plan their dissemination and communication actions accurately. It provides the overall scope of these activities and the role which is expected to be played by the different partners.
- **Chapter 2** breaks down the dissemination activities into detailed tables indicating the key messages, the reference stakeholders and the dissemination tools to correctly reach each target community. It is necessary to point out that this work is performed at M3 of the project and might be subject to changes as the project proceeds. The chapter includes a first timeline to share within the consortium the dissemination activities phases.
- **Chapter 3** provides more details about which dissemination tools partners can rely on during the project's execution to engage their stakeholders: as RELIANCE consortium as a whole and individual partners.
- **Chapter 4** will provide a short overview of the Open Call that will be issued at M9 of the project to extend the RELIANCE services user base. This is a critical aspect to be considered while enlarging the RELIANCE services user base.
- **Chapter 5** provides information about project partners initiatives as well as meetings and events to be attended. This has to be considered the most dynamic section of the document and will be properly updated in time.

1.1 Objective of the dissemination activities

Dissemination actions aim to support all Project Work Packages (WPs), ensuring maximum visibility, accessibility and impact of the project activities. In the context RELIANCE, dissemination actions will:

- Work in close cooperation with the project technical work-packages to promote the Research Object, Data Cube and Text Mining services RELIANCE provides.
- Coordinate RELIANCE scientific partners to extend the user base of RELIANCE services within and across their user communities.
- Ensure the widest dissemination of RELIANCE services within the EOSC framework

Communication actions will make both the RELIANCE actions and results publicly available in different formats and styles. In this sense, tailored dissemination activities will be designed to make the project outcomes visible and accessible to the different target stakeholders. As from the project proposal initial plan, stakeholders have been identified and will be targeted by the dissemination and communication activities. They are summarized in terms of main clusters, examples and motivations in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Stakeholders clusters, examples and motivation

1.1.1 EOSC scientific community and projects

Motivation: RELIANCE project proposes high level services to support multiple sectors in the environmental sciences focusing not only on Earth Sciences and Earth Observation but including

engineering, data modelling, existing data infrastructures, climate modelling experts and ICT branches that analyse a wide variety of environmental problems and potential solutions. Maximum visibility in this sense has to be ensured for RELIANCE services and demonstrative scenarios within the EOSC framework, including open science communities, EOSC projects and EOSC service providers. This has to be considered the main target of the entire dissemination and communication plan.

Aim: The main aim is to disseminate RELIANCE services and methods among these scientific communities and foster international collaborations.

Identification: Stakeholder will be targeted through a dedicated dissemination strategy that is outlined all across this document. A database of conferences and workshops has been developed and displayed in its current state of evolution to ensure proper targeting of the strategy, a. It will be integrated with the list of publications, research areas and contacts acquired during the activities.

1.1.2 *Industry*

Motivation: research activities performed by scientific communities using RELIANCE Services can foster industrial applications which would take our scientific outcomes as an input to develop and implement innovative solutions for a sustainable planet or for emergency management. A valid example to be brought in this context – based on the original RELIANCE idea shown in the project proposal - is the tourism industry. This sector could leverage on studies performed by the Atmospheric and Maritime communities about the effects of COVID19 pandemics on our environment to develop innovative strategies for sustainable tourism.

Aim: The aim is to progressively involve non-Earth Science communities in the project leveraging on the capacity of RELIANCE services – and Research Object in particular as a mean to share information throughout disciplines – to allow sharing, co-creating, re-using of research findings for other purposes.

Identification: Several categories of industrial stakeholders have been identified during the project proposal, including e.g., universities studying the impact of tourism on natural environments. Additional activities to identify industrial partners will be performed throughout the project to be targeted and involved in the RELIANCE open call, issued at month 9 (September 2021).

1.1.3 *Policy Makers*

Motivation: research activities results can be of great interest for local, national and international administrations. This is particularly true when studies are carried out – using RELIANCE services – to analyse our environment and the impact of anthropogenic activities. Their interest can be the key for services adoption – or funding for service related studies – ensuring their sustainability over time.

Aim: The aim is to keep authorities – starting from specific local authorities e.g., Municipality of Venice – updated about the scientific outcomes of RELIANCE scientific scenarios.

Identification: The consortium will evaluate possible synergies with local authorities via direct contact throughout the project. This will depend on the proper evolution of RELIANCE scientific scenarios on one side and the involvement of additional players after the open call is issued.

1.1.4 *Earth Monitoring Programmes*

Motivation: the consortium expertise on Earth Observation – especially Copernicus - data management, exploitation, processing and dissemination is one of the core assets of the RELIANCE partnership. This has to be considered in all its potential as an extra contribution to bring into the EOSC-Hub services framework.

Aim: The aim is to progressively build a RELIANCE reference for the EOSC-HUB user communities as expert services providers for Copernicus data.

Identification: Constant cooperation with the Copernicus data services infrastructure and the DICE project within EINFRA7 H2020 framework.

1.1.5 *Citizens*

Motivation: RELIANCE Scientific scenarios have been meticulously crafted to create interest outside the scientific domain, stimulating citizens and schools' interest in particular.

Aim: The goal is to create awareness and curiosity through the RELIANCE scenarios and results.

Identification: Citizens will be targeted through project standard communication channels. Opportunities for wider dissemination as project services and results are ready to be disseminated will be evaluated.

1.2 *Dissemination players*

All project partners are involved in the implementation of dissemination activities. The peculiarity of the INFRAEOSC7 call and the EOSC environment requests **technical partners** and **project coordination** to be constantly connected to the EOSC-Hub framework. In particular, it is requested to create a INFRAEOSC7 project stack for a coordinated infra-project joint dissemination channel. This aspect will be implemented by closely working in synergy with the other projects funded under A1 to A5 under the same call to avoid overlaps and fragmentation.

The **scientific communities** will represent the innovator's community in charge of extending the RELIANCE service early adopters user base. Their objective will be to engage new researchers and stimulate a sense of ownership about the ideas and suggestions for RELIANCE services adoption resulting from a previous internal community discussion. In this sense, RELIANCE scientific user

communities are the core element of dissemination activities to maximize RELIANCE and EOSC service portfolio adoption in the Open Science scientific domain. RELIANCE scientific communities bring three main area of expertise and demonstrative scenarios:

- Maritime community represented by CNR-ISMAR
- Atmospheric community represented by University of Oslo
- Geohazard community represented by INGV

Each community brings its own peculiarities to the project with regard e.g., to how scientists are working together, how different agencies interact and cooperate on an Earth Science theme or topic, or how they communicate with external stakeholders both in the governmental or the public sector. The final goal of communicating how RELIANCE services can help them improve their work and their way of communicating and sharing results with each other.

1.3 RELIANCE community and capacity building

Prior to reaching external scientific user communities is the correct creation of an internal communication between service developers and scientific communities who will adopt them in their daily work. In this sense, transversal activities have been implemented since M2 by creating dedicated RELIANCE **Task Forces** that bring together scientists and service developers to build a common interpretation and vocabulary about RELIANCE service offering and usage.

The internal activity will further develop during the incoming months – as service provision reaches the first delivery phase - in the form of internal **webinars and training/ hackathons**. On one side, this approach will consolidate RELIANCE user's capacity for service adoption and be crucial to identify and develop the core messages and training materials that are needed to involve new communities that are not familiar with the concept of Research Objects, Data Cube or Text Mining.

The internal activity will prepare therefore the ground in terms of contents and approach for a **series of workshops and further training activities** for external early adopters. This will be the key to facilitate as much as possible the assimilation and exploitation of the project results and to engage new scientific communities in using RELIANCE services.

1.4 Keeping the consortium up top date for dissemination and communication activities

WP2 activities foresee a constant sharing of information with all other work packages. The dissemination matrix – see next chapter – is implemented as an online shared document that constantly monitors and updates key messages, stakeholders, engagement, and participation to meetings and events. A direct link between WP2 and WP1 ensures proper management of the project website as well as the coordination of partners participation in meetings.

Bi-weekly meetings have been organized since the project Kick Off to keep the consortium updated on dissemination activities through reporting (e.g., new contacts, invitation to meetings) as well as to

share and inspire the story-telling for social media channels which will involve all partners with specific messages for their targets.

1.5 COVID-19 provisions

Due to the coronavirus pandemic threat and the vaccination campaign in its debut in Europe, each communication and dissemination activity that would generally require physical attendance and important logistics implications will be carefully assessed in consultation with the hosting authorities, the coordinator and the PO (Project Officer), by putting RELIANCE consortium staff's health safety in the first place.

Decisions taken will range from full participation with social distancing and the use of PPE (Protective Personal Equipment), to alternative solutions (run fully or partially virtual), /postponement/cancellation in the worst-case scenario.

Contingency actions will be then carefully planned case by case. They will be tailored according to the development of the events in order to carry out the planned activities in a way that it could be as close as to an in-person meeting as we could possibly have, abiding to safety conditions. This would possibly require more than a standard remote call with talks. Organisers should consider more interactive systems within which virtual participation could become more enjoyable and socialising.

2 Building the dissemination strategy

This chapter is the core element of the dissemination and communication plan. Throughout the next paragraphs, the work is conceived as follows:

- The **Key messages** table derives the Key Messages from the main project objectives. We need to ensure that each time we decide a specific Objective has to be disseminated to external stakeholders, the related specific key messages are included throughout the chosen dissemination tool (e.g., presentation, newsletter, social media). Additional specific Key messages will be integrated as they are identified during the internal activities as core elements for a wider RELIANCE service adoption
- The **Stakeholder Table** identifies the user communities – both general and specific – that the RELIANCE project is intending to connect with. In this sense, the table will also contain the grouping of key messages that the project shall deliver to each target community. This is important to be defined in detail as not all communities might be interested in the same perspective of our project: Key messages have to be customized for each target.
- The **Dissemination Channels** table is a direct consequence and synthesis of the first two tables described above and provides the project communication plan: it specifies which dissemination channels have to be used to target a specific stakeholder with one particular key message.

It is important to mention that the Stakeholder Table and the Key Messages table are used as the starting point to build the **Project/ Initiatives relevant for Networking** and **Meetings and events** chapters. The latter are – for document readability – reported at the end and will be constantly updated throughout the project timeline.

The work summarised in the following tables has been carried out throughout M1 and M3, welcoming all consortium members as an internal community-building activity under WP2 coordination. The proposed exercise has been to discuss and identify together who they consider to be their relevant stakeholders and what are the key messages the project has to deliver as a consortium and/or as a single entity participating into the RELIANCE initiative.

2.1 *The Key messages*

Key messages are grouped in terms of Project Objectives. The same terminology will summarize the key messages to be delivered to each target group in the dedicated paragraph.

Project objectives	Description	Specific Key Messages
Objective 1	Provision of a rich suite of services for Research Lifecycle Management in accordance with FAIR principle based on Research Objects, Data Cubes and Text Mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RELIANCE as a set of Research Lifecycle Management dedicated services for Copernicus Users to be integrated into EOSC • RELIANCE Services are interconnected • Research Objects have to be considered a mean to aggregate information about research activities • Text Mining Service: RELIANCE will provide AI functionalities to dig into publications and extract coherent and relevant information - to be embedded into RO's informative content. • Data Cubes as a service enhancing Earth Observation data visualization. • Data Cube to be incorporated into RO's to provide state of the art technology for EO data management and exploitation • RELIANCE will enhance multi-disciplinary research: cross fertilization throughout different disciplines. • Scientist will be able to self-assess the FAIR-Ness of their research
Objective 2	Integration and onboarding of RELIANCE research enabling services in EOSC, leveraging and connecting with other complementary EOSC services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RELIANCE services are available and orderable by all EOSC Users • AAI compliance and federation • RELIANCE services to be integrated into the EGI Cloud • RELIANCE will work to ensure services full integration with other EOSC essential such as B2Share, Zenodo, etc. • Project engagement with EOSC technology providers and the EOSC digital innovation hub • Maximize Research Object dissemination through cooperation and synergy with Open Aire related initiatives.
Objective 3	Demonstrate the RELIANCE services and value proposition through a set of multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary case studies involving Earth Science and non-Earth Science domains.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RELIANCE services to be demonstrated by multi-disciplinary scenarios in Earth Science • Vertical ES scenarios are included with three demonstrations: Sea Monitoring, Atmospheric and Geohazard community • An additional Climate change multidisciplinary use case scenario inspired by Covid 19 consequences in terms of anthropogenic impact on our environment and sustainable actions.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The project will extend its user base outside the pure Earth Science community: external stakeholders' inclusion (open call) as a key element of the RELIANCE.
Objective 4	Foster the adoption of Copernicus data and services in such scientific communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RELIANCE scientific communities and EO data experts as drivers for networking and enlarging the technology user base of Copernicus data and RELIANCE services Focus on the possibility of interdisciplinarity and cross-fertilization across and among Earth Science Foster the Open Science and FAIR data approach and adoption RELIANCE service as a reliable asset/ tool to improve researchers working methodologies

Table 1 RELIANCE Key messages

2.2 RELIANCE stakeholders

The following table shows the target groups identified by project partners for dissemination activities. The table indicates - for each target group - what are the relevant bodies/ organizations to be contacted and the specific key messages the consortium is willing to disseminate.

The table includes, where deemed necessary, a pre-requirement final column: this has to be intended as a constraint for the dissemination activity for a specific target to start only under certain conditions.

As an example: reaching RELIANCE services early adopters – i.e., new communities - shall be done taking into careful account the services state of the art in terms of implementation and deployment: to ensure services can be presented and then effectively used by the new communities and not disseminated as a *to be implemented* service diagram.

Target group	Relevant Bodies	Key Messages	Pre-requirements
EINFRA7 projects	OpenAire Nexus, DICE, C-SCALE, EGI-ACE	Objective 1, 3, 4 Key Messages	
EOSC community	EOSC services providers, EGI, EOSC Earth Science players	Objective 1, 3, 4 Key Messages	
Sea monitoring community	Ifremer, MIO-ECSDE, CNRS, CNR; STICHTING DELTARES Netherlands, Venice Lagoon Plastic Free Italy, Centro Internazionale in Monitoraggio Ambientale - Fondazione CIMA IT, FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION Spain, CIIMAR - Centro Interdisciplinar de Investigação Marinha e Ambiental –	Objective 1, 3, 4 Key Messages	Service 1 st delivery

	Portugal, CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS France, The Rivers Trust UK, Centro Tecnológico Naval y del Mar CTN-Marine Technology Centre SPAIN		
Marine strategy stakeholders	Venice Lagoon Plastic Free Italy, Centro Internazionale in Monitoraggio Ambientale - Fondazione CIMA IT, CIIMAR - Centro Interdisciplinar de Investigação Marinha e Ambiental – Portugal	Objective 1, 3, 4 Key Messages. Demonstrate Effectiveness of RO for Marine Strategy indicators	Service 1 st delivery
Geohazard Community	European & Italian Civil protections, VAAC, volcanological observatories, local governments, European and Non-European University and research centres, aviation agencies, Supersite community (European and non-European), VDAP-USGS, GEOVOL association (Center-South America)	Objective 1, 3, 4 Key Messages. Effectiveness of RO for Geohazard. Near real time monitoring of volcanic clouds by remote sensing	Services 1 st delivery
EOSC Nordic	Infrastructure providers (Sigma-2, SNIC, CSC, DelC)	Objective 1,3,4 Key Messages	RO Hub implementation
Galaxy Community	University of Freiburg, Galaxy Global Steering Committee	Objective 1,2,4 Key Messages. Use of data cube RO, "integration of ROs/ROHUB" in Galaxy	To be discussed further
Language technologies in science community	Elsevier, Carnegie Mellon	Objective 1. Focus on Text Mining	
RO community	RO working group, RO crate	Objective 1, 3, 4. Focus on Research Objects Promote RELIANCE Services, RELIANCE as leader of RO in Earth Science-EOSC	

Ecologists (fields ecologists & modellers)	NGEE-Tropics, EMERALD-UiO, Natural History Museum (Oslo, Paris), GBIF	Objective 1, 3, 4. Focus on Data Cube perspective in RELIANCE. Use of ROs within their research workflow, Use of ADAM platform	Services 1 st delivery
Climate Community	Nordic Earth System Modelling (NICEST2), INES (Norway), KeyCLIM (Norway), MetNO, SMHI, NILU, CICERO and other Research institutes in Norway, IndiCol (Norway), MEDEC, STICHTING DELTARES Netherlands, FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION Spain, UNIVERSITATEA POLITEHNICA DIN BUCURESTI RO, The Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP) UNESCO	Objective 1, 3, 4 Key Messages	Services 1 st delivery
Open Science community / STI	SINTEF AS Norway, The Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP) UNESCO, UNESCO Office in Beijing	Objective 1, 3, 4 Key Messages. Adoption of ROs to improve/foster Open Science practices; Targeting ICTP scientific community in developing countries to potential overcome the isolation that still impacts them and serve to specific needs: (i)have access to open and affordable solutions to carry out their research and (ii)communicate with their peers and (iii)build the	Services 1 st delivery

		capacity necessary to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).	
Users of Climate data (not from the climate community)	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	Objective 1, 3, 4 Key Messages. Focus on Open Call	Services 1 st delivery
EOSC-Life	WP9 EOSC-Life	Objective 2. Adoption of ROs, open calls, advertise our project and events	
Data infrastructures	ICDI, ESA TEP	Objective 2. Adoption of ROs, open calls, advertise our project and events	
GEOHAZARDS Research Centres / Disaster Risk Management	National Research Council (National public research institution) IRPI-IGAG Italy, UNIVERSITA TA MALTA MT (Georisk seismology), Centro Internazionale in Monitoraggio Ambientale - Fondazione CIMA IT	Objective 1, 3, 4 Engagement of DRM scientific community in geohazard investigation for prevention and mitigation	Services 1 st delivery

Table 2 RELIANCE Stakeholders

2.3 Dissemination channels

Next table provides evidence of which channels are going to be used for each target group.

Dissemination Channel	Target Group	Description
Website	All groups	Website as the main project visibility tools Specific sections on Services/ EOSC integration/ Scientific scenarios to target related stakeholders Weekly news to be inserted on the landing page
Twitter	All groups	Around 5 tweets per week to describe <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team internal work • Project evolution

	Particular attention to keep a stable connection with EINFRA7 twitter account and other RELIANCE partners projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RELIANCE Challenges • Scientific scenarios evolution • Each RELIANCE Services evolution • Dedicated narrative related to Copernicus data management and exploitation capabilities • Show RELIANCE services capabilities in other contexts (e.g., ADAM)
LinkedIn	All scientific communities and EOSC players on LinkedIn	Maximise researchers' interest via weekly news. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Re-Post website news • Create discussions on RO, Data Cube, Text Mining • Participate to EOSC related groups
Newsletter	EOSC, EINFRA7, Scientific Communities, RO Community	Overall updates on project advancement and challenges
Brochures	N/A	Depends on Pandemic evolution
Posters	N/A	Depends on Pandemic evolution
Webinars	EINFRA7 project, scientific communities, EOSC	Internal webinars as well as webinars or to engage the EOSC projects/ services providers
Scientific papers	Scientific communities	To be delivered into thematic scientific meetings (see meeting and events)
Training	RELIANCE Early adopters among scientific communities.	
Direct e-mail	Galaxy community	To further discuss potential RO and RELIANCE services adoption.
EOSC Portal	EINFRA7 and EOSC scientific communities	Showcase RELIANCE services
Project Presentation	EINFRA7 and EOSC framework	Explain the role of RELIANCE services into the EOSC context.
Info Video	Open science community, IGO's, Early Adopters	To familiarize with RELIANCE Services
Scientific presentations	Scientific communities	Supporting RELIANCE scientific partners in their dissemination actions

Table 3 RELIANCE dissemination channels

2.4 Dissemination timeline

The following image shows the overall project activities timeline.

Figure 2 RELIANCE timeline summary

The project timeline identifies breaks the project in two main segments: from M1 to M12 (1st RELIANCE Service Release) and then from M12 to M24.

During **Phase 1**, the project will focus on RELIANCE services development and will support the use case scenarios grand challenges to be addressed by the three open multidisciplinary Earth Science communities. From the dissemination and communication perspective, the project will keep a constant dialogue with other EOSC-Hub services providers and the EINFRA7 initiatives. Scientific communities will disseminate the RELIANCE project and main ideas through their dissemination channels. A strong focus will be on internal capacity building: communities will participate in co-designing multi-disciplinary Research Lifecycle scenarios for the specific use cases and research objectives (via co-creation webinars). The first phase will include the steps to cooperate with IGO's. The consortium will set out and publish the **open call** "RELIANCE Challenge" by M9 in order : i) selection of specific topic related to Lockdown Grand Challenges to be addressed by the call for proposals through a dedicated Workshop; ii) identification of non-Earth Science expertise area to be identified related to the Grand Challenge, iii) design of the call for the inclusion of new adopters to be enrolled by M13, including the term of references; iv) publication and dissemination of the call; v) establishment of a committee for the project selection.

During **Phase 2**, the consortium will maximise its dissemination and communication effort to the external scientific and technical communities leveraging on i) the availability and usability of RELIANCE services ii) the lessons learned during the internal capacity building activities in terms of messages and training methods to facilitate services early adopters take up. Following the approach of EOSC early adopters' program, the offer for the selected applicants will include mainly support, know-how, and resources iii) the evolution of the multidisciplinary scenarios iv) the integration of a new use cases based on the Open Call results.

3 Overall communication objectives and tools

Communication strategies will be used to maximize RELIANCE impact and to communicate the actions and results within and outside the consortium, thus enabling exploitation opportunities and business development. *Communication actions within and beyond the consortium will start from day one*, supporting the dissemination actions.

The **core communication actions beyond the RELIANCE consortium** aim to fulfil the following objectives:

- **Maximise the use** of the services developed by the project, raising awareness among stakeholders and educating them on how to use such services;
- **Engage** different types of stakeholders (and especially end-users), to obtain first-hand experience, requirements, and real needs that will guide the development of the project technological outcomes;
- **Explain** the potential of RELIANCE based added value services to the private sector
- Promote citizens **awareness** highlighted by the 2020 lockdown environmental impact and RELIANCE related multidisciplinary scenarios
- Highlight the importance of Research FAIR-ness, **EOSC service portfolio and Open Science** approach;
- Show how **European collaboration** through the consortium fosters innovation, increases European competitiveness, and produces important outcomes relevant to our everyday lives and aims to tackle the main societal challenges.
- **Cooperate with the other selected projects** awarded under the same topic

3.1 Visual Identity

The project visual identity – declination of the logo, presentation/ poster/ infographic layouts – has been defined in M1. The colour palette has been built around the logo idea which consortium partners have already identified.

Figure 3 RELIANCE project Logo and Lettering

Figure 4 RELIANCE Presentation Template

3.2 Website

The website will be the core element of the communication strategy, meaning that all other communication activities will link to the website to provide further support and information. As the current Covid-19 situation does not allow to foresee the certainty to arrange a traditional event in a physical location, the project will incorporate ad hoc technologies to allow the website to play the role of the *digital home* of the project. So that, for instance, online events can be arranged within the website, thus defining also places in which the potential attendants could meet to exchange opinion about the project and its application, such as virtual coffee break rooms dedicated to networking activities.

Figure 5 Landing page of RELIANCE Website

In line with H2020 roles, the website will host a section storing all the literature produced during the project including deliverables, presentations, other informative material, summary of the different events both hosted or attended including third party presentation if necessary. The website will be supported at least until 5 years after the end of the project. The website shall have backlinks from all the consortium company websites. There will be bi-weekly news update on the news section related

to any possible progress made during the development phase and then about the results as the different trials – both virtual and on the ground – will take place.

3.2.1 *Website structure*

Home: The Home page to be considered a landing page provides a brief description of all project components. The other project main pages can be accessed by the top menu. A section dedicated to engagement follows with clear "call-to-action" buttons, aiming to inform stakeholders and local communities on how they can collaborate with the Consortium and get involved in our activities

About page: The section provides all administrative information about the project, including details about the EU Grant, the consortium partners, the work packages, the project timeline and the list of deliverables that will be progressively issued by the consortium.

Services : is divided into four sections. One for each service – Research Object, Data Cube, Text Mining – going in detail on their functionalities and usage mechanism. A fourth section details how those services are going to be interconnected within the EOSC service framework.

Scientific Communities: showing details about each Scientific scenario, including the three vertical Earth Science scenarios, the multidisciplinary scenario and the future scenario provided by the Open Call.

Connect: allows website visitors to get involved into the project communications and network. This ranges to receive the RELIANCE newsletter to a more inclusive role i.e., as potential early adopter of RELIANCE Services or users of the RELIANCE demonstrative scenarios. The web page is completed by the list and references of Infrastructures, projects and EOSC Service providers RELIANCE is working in synergy with.

3.3 *Social Media*

Social Media will be used as a leading communication channel to engage interest in the project and create awareness among stakeholders. LinkedIn and Twitter will be the core Social Media for knowledge exchange with the stakeholders' clusters. The project will develop ad hoc Social media graphics: i) infographic to coherently explain specific elements of the projects, ii) social media animations, very short but delivering powerful videos to attract the users' attention.

Figure 6 @reliance_eosc twitter channel

3.4 Infographics and videos

At M3 the WP2 team is preparing an infographic animation to support scientific communities to disseminate the project throughout external stakeholders. More in general, the work has to support the creation of the Open Call, which will be issued at M9 and will have the goal to include new additional communities of EOSC early users, not necessarily directly related to Earth Science disciplines. This has the goal to enlarge the demonstrative scenarios outside the pure Earth Science domain, engage new users and demonstrate the validity of RELIANCE Services for cross-fertilization and transdisciplinary work.

Therefore, the infographic is the first simple message the consortium is circulating outside its internal community. Its objective is to simplify the message and the comprehension of RELIANCE service using real-life scenario. The story-telling adopted by the RELIANCE consortium during the proposal preparation has proven to be effective for non-RO/ Text Mining and Data Cube specialists. Therefore, the example is going to be widely replicated for the infographic. A first glimpse of the final result is depicted in the following visual storyboard which is under discussion and finalization.

Figure 7 RELIANCE infographic storyboard (M3)

3.5 Printed materials

To keep a green approach on the project and reach a highest number of people, RELIANCE will produce digital brochures and flyers to explain the project and its core elements. These tools could also include videos, external links, and interactions, and for these reasons, they become a powerful communication tool able to successfully and quickly reach the communication goals. These media are less expensive as they don't need to be printed. They are also more flexible in terms of updates, so they could be renewed several times during the evolution of the project. The project will also produce a printed version of the brochure to be used in the case of a workshop in physical locations. The production of printed materials is strictly connected to the evolution of the Pandemic crisis in 2021, and, therefore, to the opportunity to attend to face to face meetings and conferences.

3.6 Newsletter

The project will deliver a digital newsletter linked to the project website, through which the consortium will establish a stable dialogue with all the critical stakeholders interested in RELIANCE Services and approach. The newsletter will be issued every six months (using Mailchimp or equivalent software), starting four months after the kick-off and including specific newsletters in the frame of the open call, the final delivery of services and the final stage of the project. The newsletter will provide information not just upon the services, but also about the evolution of scientific scenarios related to the project. Finally, it will have a fixed section dedicated to scientific articles on the topic related to the project.

3.7 Training

Training webinars will be organized during the second phase of the project: the goal to allow services early adopters to familiarize with the use of services within the EOSC framework. As mentioned throughout the entire document webinars messages, service usage best practices will be planned and crafted during the internal community and capacity building.

3.8 Webinars

Being written during the COVID 19 crisis, the RELIANCE proposal needs to consider potential future limitations to travelling and face to face meetings. In this light, webinars represent the only consolidated alternative to guarantee proper dissemination activities, including capacity building. A set of online webinars - recorded during the project and eventually made available for targeted audience on the public website – would be needed to fully support the achievement of impacts and ensure proper training and engagement of RELIANCE services Early Adopters outside the consortium end users. The basic schedule for internal co-creation webinars includes at least the following

- One co-creation Webinar with the active participation of the end user-communities invited to collect additional input for co-design of potential services;
- One validation Webinar with the active participation of the end user-groups to validate the body of indications expressed and formulated;

3.9 Project presentations

Project’s presentations and infographics starts at M1 of the project and will evolve throughout the project activities. While the infographics will be used for general public, dissemination in support of web-related activities and social media, the presentation will target different stakeholders: from scientific to the private sector to the general public domain. The language and length of the presentation will be customized accordingly to the targets.

3.10 Communication Timeline

Communication actions through project lifetime are summarised in the following picture, dividing between the continued activity – grey boxes – and the One Time Activities, which depend on the project evolution.

Figure 8 Schedule of project communication activities

3.11 Communication Matrix

The schedule of communication resources which have been proposed are shown in the next table, together with the specific time frame of the actions and the channel proposed to spread it.

Tools and actions	Channels / Place	Communication goal
Visual identity	Web, social media, presentations, brochure	Create awareness
Website	Web	Engage and inform
Social media graphic, animations and messages	Social media	Attract, Inform and Engage
Newsletter	Web	Inform and establish a stable dialogue with all the stakeholders
Video	Web, Social, Conferences (TBD)	Engage and retain

Tools and actions	Channels / Place	Communication goal
Project presentations	Web and conferences	Inform
Workshop support	Conferences	Create a dialogue with the stakeholders and retain interest
Scientific and not press release and conferences	Web and press	Inform and increase awareness

Table 4 Communication Matrix

KPI #	Description	Target
1	Number accesses to the web portal access	600 per month
2	Number of articles spread over web, press and magazines	3 per month
3	Number of visualisations of the informative videos on website (infographics)	200 per month
4	Open rate percentage of the newsletter	35%
5	Number of searches of the word RELIANCE in the search engine	100 per month

Table 5 Communication KPI'

4 The Open Call

The consortium will launch with the support of the International research networks and with the IGOs (case in point UNESCO) an open call for applicants under the title of “RELIANCE Challenge” to extend the user base and multidisciplinary approach. In this context, RELIANCE will also operate, for instance, synergic interaction with:

- the **H2020 project “Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud” (SSHOC)** developing the social sciences and humanities area in EOSC.
the **international EOSC community use case on Environmental and health sciences** aiming at attracting researchers from Africa and China to use EOSC services on top of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CNIC) resources.
- The **World Summit on the Information Society (WSIS) Forum**, a UN multi stakeholder platform
- facilitating the implementation of the sustainable development goals
- The **Global Alliance of Open Access to Scholarly Communication Platform (CGOALL)**.
- platform was launched by UNESCO and partners and is meant to democratize scientific knowledge
- following a multicultural, multi-thematic and multi-lingual approach.

The beneficiaries for a period of 6 to 12 months will get:

- Know how support, from RELIANCE experts providing the services, to introduce them, engage them
- and enabling them to use EOSC resources for advanced data-driven research;
- Support from expert staff providing the services, which will enable integrating activities with the EOSC
- resources;
- The technical infrastructure needed for piloting the experiments. This will include the access to
- resources like data, applications, software, and other services required from EOSC, depending on the
- research community needs;
- Resources for processing data using the methods of the case study, and for long term archiving of data and results aggregated via the Research Objects

5 Project/ Initiatives relevant for Networking

Project	Description	Target Groups	AIM
Blue cloud project		Sea monitoring community, Marine strategy	Synergies, complement our services in EOSC, Interoperability
Aristotle (DG-ECHO project)		Technologic community, Scientific community, civil protections	Use early warning system tool from NRT detections of volcanic clouds
EPOS		seismology community, GNSS community + remote sensing community and volcano observatory community	connect EPOS infrastructure (e.g., portals dedicated to in situ data) with reliance (e.g., get data from WPS), propose RO concept, share metadata formats
Cheese - EU project		Seismology, Tsunami and Volcanology HPC codes developers and implementers	Connect their activities to EOSC, check their simulators for volcanic clouds for comparisons with 'our' estimations based on remote sensing data, propose RO concept, in general synergies
VISTA		Geohazard community	Synergies, complement our services in EOSC, Interoperability
HARMONIA		Geohazard community and multidisciplinary community (e.g., climate change	Check the infrastructure and propose RO and Interoperability, synergies
DARE		seismology community, also climate community (IS-ENES3)	check their infrastructure and see whether there is anything that we can build on
EGI-ACE		EInfra07 Project cluster	Synergies and close collaboration with sister InfraEOSC07 project, promote

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			results and leverage results
OPENAIRE-Nexus		EInfra07 Project cluster	Synergies and close collaboration with sister InfraEOSC07 project, promote results and leverage results
DICE		EInfra07 Project cluster	Synergies and close collaboration with sister InfraEOSC07 project, promote results and leverage results
C-SCALE		EInfra07 Project cluster	Synergies and close collaboration with sister InfraEOSC07 project, promote results and leverage results
EOSC ENHANCE		All Open Science communities	Onboard some of our services. Propose our own metadata models there

6 Meetings and events

Event	Description	Target Groups	Role	Aim
EOSC Nordic Annual meeting	once a year meeting in, website	EOSC Nordic, Atmospheric community,	Session	Maximise our chance for disseminating RELIANCE into the EOSC Nordic Framework
EGU 2021	EGU Europe	Supersites, Atmospheric community, Sea monitoring, EOSC community	Presentation	RELIANCE Services showcase
EGU 2022	EGU Europe	Supersites, Atmospheric community, Sea monitoring, EOSC community	Presentation and posters for each community; Geohazard session organized	RELIANCE Services showcase
Workshop on Scholarly document processing	Next to keeping up with the growing literature in their own and related fields, scholars increasingly also need to rebut pseudo-science and disinformation. To address these challenges, computational work on enhancing search, summarization, and analysis of scholarly documents has flourished.	Language technologies in science community	Workshop: all reliance partners	Gain traction in the community and create awareness
eScience conference		RO community	Presentation	Project showcase
IGARSS 2021	International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium	Geohazard community, Supersite Community, remote sensing community	Presentation and poster	Project showcase
IAVCEI 2022	International Association of Volcanology and Chemistry of the Earth's Interior	Geohazard community, Supersite Community, remote sensing community	Session organized; poster & oral presentation	Project showcase
COV 2021	Cities on Volcanoes meeting	Geohazard community, Supersite Community,	Session organized;	Project showcase

		remote sensing community	poster & oral presentation	
EUMETSAT IASI 2021	ASI (Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer)	Geohazard community, Supersite Community, remote sensing community	poster & oral presentation	Project showcase
CVC 2022 (2021 maybe)	International school on convective volcanic clouds organized by INGV	Geohazard community, Supersite Community, remote sensing community	Organized by INGV	Project showcase
VDAP-GEOVOL 2022 (2021 maybe)	Annual meeting of the Latin America association of volcanic geodesy, supported by VDAP (USGS - USA)	Geohazard community, Supersite Community, remote sensing community	INGV has 1-2 full-days for remote sensing techniques & hands-on sessions	Showcase our services + dissemination with users

6.1 List of Meeting and Events attended at M3

N°	Date	Venue	Event/ Project	Presenter
1	5.2.2021	On line https://indico.egi.eu/event/5359/	EGI/ ACE: Public launch event	Raul Palma
2	3.3.2021	On line https://events.geant.org/event/546/	GEANT	Raul Palma
3	10.3.2021	On line https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-nexus-public-launch-event	OpenAire-Nexus: Public launch event	Raul Palma
4.	11.3.2021	On line https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vg805CJ4QXY6CCBNR-8ETgkbOCAMqSKJPCKOTNxrIbk/edit	RO-crate: EOSC community call	Raul Palma
5.	18.3.2021	On line	OpenAire-Nexus: Bilateral (OpenAire-Nexus – RELIANCE) projects synergies identification	Raul Palma Oscar Corcho José Manuel Gómez Pérez Esteban Garcia Daniel Garijo Malgorzata Wolni ewicz

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6	18.3.2021	On line	Advisory Board: Bilateral information exchange with Sheila JJ Heymans, Executive Director European Marine Board	Federica Foglini Raul Palma
7.	15.3.2021	On line	Synergies teleconference with Chris Atherton Senior Research Engagement Officer GÉANT	Raul Palma Pedro Gonçalves Simone Mantovani

7 Conclusions

Stakeholders' engagement of the RELIANCE project calls for a thorough analysis and planning. Thus, a significant effort is placed on compiling databases to identify each stakeholder and settle the targeting. In addition, a transversal effort will be the generation of a sensitive community database including areas that reliance solutions and related demonstrative scenarios can make a high impact.

The **dissemination** strategy leverages the Consortium's combined expertise to access different areas of knowledge through publications, workshops, and conference attendance.

The **communication** strategy is diverse in formats, reach and scope. It ranges from audio-visual material to explaining the project to a large audience to the more technical account of the project progresses through the newsletter. As a markedly innovative action, the Consortium has proposed setting up social accounts that will generate information to a wider community. At long last, these social media accounts will serve to publicise the project's achievement and contribute to increasing the possibilities of RELIANCE services adoption

Overall, this plan accounts for the Consortium's multifaceted global strategy to reach multiple audiences and make stakeholders count as another partner of the Consortium. The updates and initial results of the communication and dissemination plan will be included in Deliverable D2.4 at M12.